

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.448 Max: 63.678	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1402 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	 Gabil Project
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In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 2168 75	Photo Model: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 319
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DEFINITION Small east of corridor SU 1322	Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1016	Fills <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1476	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX		
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive	
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft	Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)		Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Western Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by: 1279, 1383, 1385	Abuts: 1032
Is covered by: 1016	Covers:
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills: 1476

OBSERVATIONS SU was visible in 2008, but properly excavated in 2011

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: Trench Central through eastern part of Trench B 2011
Shape: linear with irregular extension to the east

For layers complete this section:
Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions):
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope):
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):
Nature of the interface with layer below: <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commingled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:	Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):
Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight	
Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping	
Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular	
How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded	
How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded	
Observations:	

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment: (Side) N-S

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) Irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size: Small (range) 6x6 cm Medium (range) 15x20 cm Large (range) 40x40 cm Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing: _____

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Floor/revetment type: _____

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Length = _____
 Width = 20-40 cm

Height (from top to bottom of sewer) = ca. 70 cm

Description:

Consists of mainly irregular stones, though some tufo blocks are worked. Mostly tufo, but a few basalt + travertine stones are visible. Where there are worked stones the lining is very regular, elsewhere (especially to the north + south) it is irregular + in fact difficult to follow.

INTERPRETATION

Stone lining of a drainage channel (SU 1322), rather a lining than a wall. SU 1402 is faced towards drainage channel (west-facing) and had been cut into layers 1032, 1389.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by J. Farr

on 2.8.2011

Revised by CMH

on 3.8.2011

PDFd by ER

on 3.8.2011

Entered by

on